

ZeroW has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 101036388.

**Funded by
the European Union**

0FLW dataspace

The 0FLW Dataspace is an architectural concept for secure sharing data among organisations who have joined forces, resources and means in general.

It will enable the exchange of data easier, in a shorter amount of time, with lesser costs and required specialised expertise, while remaining full control over privacy and the data.

The implementation of a 0FLW dataspace will result in a generic IT infrastructure where information and business services can be found and shared in a secure and trusted way, based on standardized technical, semantical and organisational solutions to help reducing waste.

At the end of the project an operational organisation will take care of the 0FLW data ecosystem and look after the interest of the ZeroW community. ■